

Assessing Factors that Influence Teenagers' Involvement in Gambling Activities in Tanzania: A Case of Tandika Ward of Temeke District, Dar es Salaam - Tanzania

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Abstract:

Gambling is not a new phenomenon in the society and to the field of scholars. The subject has been in existence since the ancient societies, nevertheless it has gained popularity with more human interactions and modernization. Of late, gambling has gained attention due to the age problem in which there is a concern of growing numbers of teenagers who engage in gambling activities. The main aim of this study was to assess the factors for increasing teenagers' involvement in gambling activities. Thus, the objective of the study was to examine the effectiveness of legislation in controlling teenage gambling. The explorative study was conducted

in Temeke district of Dar es salaam and it engaged both qualitative and quantitative methods. A sample of 99 participants was selected through simple random sampling, snow ball sampling and convenience sampling. The study employed in-depth interview and questionnaire to collect information that enabled the writing of this paper. Qualitative data was analyzed by use of thematic data analysis methods while quantitative data was analyzed with graphs and percentages of responses as well as paragraph explanations. The findings revealed that there are legislative factors that influence teenagers involvement into gambling activities, the factors include: ineffectiveness of Tanzania Gambling Act (TGA) of 2006, ineffectiveness of Gaming Board of Tanzania (GBT), District Administrative Secretary (DAS) office, and Ward Executive Offices (WEO). The study recommended that the government should review the policies and clearly stipulate further restrictions and repercussions on areas concerning teenagers and/or under age involvement in gambling activities. Through the Regional Administration and Local Government Authority (RALG) departments and Ministry of Education Science and Technology (MoEST) to design awareness programs to the public and sensitize members of public on social and economic adverse effects of gambling to teenagers. Parents should be encouraged to be responsible and accountable for the behaviors of their children. Also, the local government authorities should be training in technology aspects and equipped with resources to execute better on their roles in the communities.

Keywords: *Gambling, teenagers, technology.*

Introduction

Gambling is described as the betting or staking of something of value, with clear knowledge of risk and hope of gain, on the outcomes of a game, a contest, or an uncertain event whose result may be determined by chance or accident or have an unexpected result because of the bettor's miscalculation. Gambling has been widely studied both in international and local realms due to the fact that it is a fast-growing part of the life experiences of most young people (Hollen et al, 2020). Nevertheless, it has been taking place in different forms in the past times and is inextricably linked to the history of humanity.

Among the most known gambling games, playing cards first appeared in China in the 9th century, and the cards bore some resemblance to those used today which gives evidence of the genesis of the activities from that time. In ancient China, indications of rudimentary games of chance were also discovered on tiles just the same way the oldest known dice were excavated in Egypt. Other evidences indicate that betting on animal fights was common and animals would be bred for that sole purpose. In around 200 BC 'white pigeon ticket' was played in gambling houses of China with the permission of the province governor, who would receive a percentage of the profits, and the winnings were often used to fund state works; Even Harvard and Yale were both initially funded using lottery money, which they continue to use today (Cormack, 2018).

At the height of technology in later decades, gambling has become more organized and regulated with the first casinos or gambling houses first appearing in Italy in the 17th century as one of the major landmarks. The first gambling machine was developed by Sittman and Pitt in New York, and around the same time, the Liberty Bell machine was invented by Charles Fey in San Francisco (Frometa, 2021). The first video slot was invented in 1976 which paved the way for the online video slots that followed.

In Tanzania, all gaming activities are regulated under the Tanzania Gaming Act (TGA, 2006). Under the TGA of 2006, Part II, the Gaming Board of Tanzania was established and allocated functions in part II (7)-1 which include: to oversee, monitor and regulate the conduct of all gaming activities in Tanzania. In that respect, the Gaming Board of Tanzania has the mandates to offer gambling license for operators who want to enter the gambling industry; inspect; examine and assess gambling business and their premises to ensure that they adhere to and meet the set standards and regulations. The other mandates of GBT are to make sure that gaming operators conform to the gaming rules, policies, specifications and standards of the Gaming Act; inspect the registry ensuring that gaming operators are licensed ones and; to handle complaints of players. According to the gaming board, over the last six years, there is an abrupt increase in betting stations; the increase is due to various factors such as financial difficulties and the development of technology. In the financial year 2016/2017, sports betting topped the list by contributing T.shs 17.9 billion, trailed by casinos, which contributed T.shs 7.8 billion to the government budget (The Citizen, 2022). From 2014 up to 2017, the government is delighted with huge growth in collections of tax, with gaming practices producing 15.3 billion in taxes in 2014/15. The tax amount expanded progressively to T.shs 24.4 billion and T.shs 36.8 billion in 2015/16 and 2016/17, respectively. After establishing formal betting stations, particularly in Dar es Salaam, sports betting became a source of individual income for some Tanzanians. Today the most widely known and most noteworthy bet offers are set on football (soccer).

The Tanzania's Gaming Act (2006), stipulates in its chapter 41(70) (1) a, b, and c that it is unlawful for any person under the age of 18 years to be in the gaming area whether be it sitting on a gaming chair, keeping around a slot machine or any area where gaming is being conducted and any of such failure to comply is committing an offense leading to a 3 months jail term or penalty of five hundred thousand shillings or both. In spite of

the legal statement, teenagers involvement in gaming activities in Tanzania is ever increasing. It is therefore against this background that the study wants to assess factors that influence teenagers involvement in gambling activities in Tanzania.

Methodology

Research design

This study employed exploratory research design because there are very limited in-depth studies that have been conducted on this subject and most of those studies were done outside Tanzania environment and Dar es salaam in particular. The research design was specifically the roadmap of procedures that were used in the study (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It was also the blueprint that shows how data was collected, measured, and analyzed (Awe, 2022). This design was therefore the structure that shows how the study was conducted showing the procedures that lead to the findings about the study objectives. The exploratory research design has been very instrumental in arriving to the findings.

Research approach

The study employed both qualitative methods and quantitative methods hence a mixed approach was used in the study. This is because the study intended to understand the perceptions of the respondents concerning the study variables as well as the numerical aspect that includes frequency of the respondents with the experiences of teenagers gambling activities. According to Taherdoost (2022) research approach refers to the procedures and plans that show steps that are assumed to be followed in the course of the study through data collection, data analysis, and data interpretation. Qualitative methods involve the use of non-numerical data to aid in the understanding of the variables and the experiences (Bhandari, 2020). Qualitative methods were applied to gather perceptions of key respondents who had some specific in-depth information on the social experiences of the entire area of study while quantitative methods were used to gather numerical data from other

participants including the teenagers and their parents. This method focused on frequencies and statistical data concerning the occurrences of gambling activities among the population that will involve computational techniques.

Research instruments and data collection

The study was conducted using semi structured interviews and by asking the respondents with open ended questions which allowed them to pre-empt their perceptions and experiences freely during the discussions. The researcher used structured interviews considering in mind that the topic that was under study needed some specific to be exhausted when building the interview questions hence making all the anticipated information about the variables retrieved. Thus, the interview guides were used to conduct the interviews with the Local government officers and the officers from the District Administrative office. Also, questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from the respondents. These were designed with close-ended and open-ended questions with alternative answers from which the respondent were required to choose an appropriate answer. Each respondent was required to answer the same question in a pre-determined order. The respondents filled out the questionnaires in written form and the researcher collected back the forms that were initially distributed to the respondents. Questionnaires were thus used to collect data from the teachers, teenagers, and parents of teenagers who were involved in the study.

Sample selection

The study was conducted in Tandika ward found in Temeke district at Dar es salam region. The study area was well known for a high population of 1,205,949 according to the national census of 2022 (URT, 2022). The study population included; secondary school administrators, teachers, and students in Tandika, residents of Tandika, and the District administrative secretary's office workers. The study population was the units or groups of selected individuals that have one or several characteristics of interest for a study that needed to be investigated. The selected respondents were

from groups of people who were dealing either directly with teenagers in schools or indirectly as regulators in the community where the teenagers live. In the study, convenience sampling technique was used to select 10 teachers who were free and available at the school at the time of conducting the study to answer the questionnaires. Purposive sampling was used to select a sample of six (6) respondents who are the local government officers and the respondents from the office of DAS. A simple random technique enabled the selection of 60 teenagers who are students to reduce biases and enable the collection of accurate and valid data and; snowball technique was used in the selection of parents who have got teenage children because it is not easy for the researcher to identify the needed participants directly.

Data analysis procedures

Data was analysed to bring order, structure, and format of the findings or raw data to derive meaning and relevance to the findings (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Data analysed and presented in a manner that allows responding to research questions and meeting the objectives of the study.

A thematic analysis approach was used in analyzing the qualitative data. The coding involved the development of concepts, the data was split into discrete elements to expose underlying thoughts and meanings. The generated codes were further interpreted and categorized into descriptive codes. These latter codes were then distilled into abstract analytical themes around which results were presented. The researchers focused on a few key issues as analyzed to be themed. Also, quantitative analysis was used to analyse the data, in quantitative analysis the researcher used frequencies, percentages as well as mean averages in the presentation of the results. The researcher further used graphs as well as tables in the presentation of the findings.

Validity

Validity is referred to as the effectiveness of the research approach in addressing the research questions of the study and coming up with the

desired outcomes (Enago, 2022). The study using a mixed design ensured that the data collection methods included both qualitative methods and quantitative methods. The study carried out pre-testing among the researcher's network or close friends, and in case of any weaknesses and gaps, the data collection instruments adjusted accordingly

Reliability

Reliability is the aptitude of the research instruments to give similar results each time they are applied to the respondents (Surucu & Maslakci, 2020). The said instruments are tested for bias and if they have consistency in measuring the intended variables in a study. This study tested and retested the research instruments before applying them in the field. Also, the researcher triangulated the instruments that were used in data collection.

Results and Discussion

Effectiveness of legislation in controlling teenage gambling

The results of the study were based on the core objective of; examining effectiveness of the legislation in controlling teenagers' involvement in gambling activities. In Tanzania, there are regulatory frameworks such as the Tanzania Gaming Act 2006, Gaming Board of Tanzania and the Local Government authorities who are mandated to ensure there is compliance in the gaming and/or gambling activities in the country. The study thus examined effectiveness of the rules and regulations in controlling the under age from engaging in gambling activities.

Effectiveness of Tanzania Gaming Act

The TGA, 2006 part 10 (70) puts a restriction on age limit at 18 years for any person to participate, loiter or make use of a chair in a gambling area and places a fine of five hundred thousand shillings or three months of imprisonment for going against the restriction. The study sought to understand aspects of awareness of the gaming act clauses and how stakeholders keep compliance to the act as far as age restrictions is concerned and avoiding teenagers from

engaging in gambling activities. The Act was also analyzed for its effectiveness to online gambling activities that are also affecting the teenagers who get massively involved in gambling. The

study therefore required the respondents to indicate the degree to which they agree with the statements on Gaming Act of 2006 and the responses are presented in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of Tanzania Gaming Act

Source: Field data, 2023

The figure 1 above shows the findings on the Gaming act of 2006 from the respondents. On awareness about the act, the majority of the respondents indicated disagree (48%) followed by neutral (39%), strongly disagree (13%), and the minority respondents indicated agree (8%). There were no respondents who indicated strongly agree.

On compliance to the act, the majority of the respondents indicated disagree (46%) which was followed by neutral (34%), agree (12%), and the minority respondents indicated strongly agree (4%) and strongly disagree (4%). The findings of the show a majority of the respondents disagree to awareness of the Act by 62% and to compliance by 50%. This shows that the Act in place is not effective as far as age limit is concerned. The findings were also analyzed in relation to how the Act restricts under age persons from engaging in gambling activities to both physical gambling and online gambling.

The act in question stipulates in part that:

“... it shall be unlawful for any person under eighteen years of age to: linger in the gaming area or casino; sit on a chair or be present at a gaming table, slot machine, or other area in which gaming is conducted; or participate, play, be allowed to play, place wagers, or collect winnings, whether personally or through an agent, in or from any gaming activity...” (TGA,2006).

The second part also states that:

“...any person who contravenes any of the provisions of the section commits an offence and any person, being an age above eighteen who permits or causes a person under eighteen years to commit an act which is prohibited under subsection (1) shall also be deemed to have committed an offence and on conviction be liable to a fine of not less than five hundred thousand shillings or

imprisonment for a term not less than three months or to both...” (TGA, 2006).

The result was not different from the outcomes of the interviews that were held in which, the respondents who are custodians to ensuring that the Act is followed admitted to not having any awareness programs in place and nor did the respondents acknowledge having any records or witnessed the custodians of the laws

apprehending and making sure that the perpetrators are brought to book. The results from the interview respondents also revealed that Act caters for physical gambling that can be monitored by the authorities but does not give any insight on the online gambling activities. The study thus determined that the TGA has not been effective in controlling teenage involvement in gambling activities most especially the online gambling.

Figure 2. Effectiveness Gaming board of Tanzania

Source: Field data, 2023

Effectiveness of Gaming Board of Tanzania

Under the TGA of 2006, Part II, the GBT was established and allocated functions in part II (7)-1 which include among others; to oversee, monitor and regulate the conduct of all gaming activities in Tanzania. It is against this function that the study wanted to understand whether the gaming board of Tanzania is effective in monitoring age compliance among the gaming stakeholders. This is through making constant inspection of the gaming places for age compliance and creating awareness to the stakeholders on issues of age compliance. The study required the respondents to indicate the degree to which they agree to the statements and the results are presented on the figure 2 above.

The figure 2 above shows the findings to which, on creating awareness about age limit in gambling places, the majority of the respondents indicated disagree (42%) followed by neutral (36%), strongly disagree (14%) and the minority respondents indicated agree (8%). There were no respondents who indicated strongly agree.

On inspection of gambling places, the majority of the respondents indicated disagree (48%) followed by neutral (28%), agree (16%), strongly disagree (6%) and the minority respondents indicated strongly agree (2%).

The study findings of the study assert with a majority standing to disagree by 52% to GBT playing the role of creating awareness to the stakeholders on age limit in gaming or gambling

places. The majority respondents also disagreed by 54% that the GBT does age inspections to the gaming places to ensure that under age individuals have entry restrictions. Similar findings were learned from the interviews that were held with the local government authorities to which, the officers had records of inspecting the gaming places to ensure that they have legal operating licenses, tax compliance and other various inspections but at the same time the officers confessed to having no clear information of GBT inspecting of these venues to check on age compliance.

One key respondent was cited as:

“...these regulators normally come to our areas to inspect on tax compliances, license validity and others. Sometimes even the police officers are seen around these places for various reasons but in my records as the street government officer, I do not have a single record of GBT coming to my area to enforce age restrictions. Not even an awareness

program. Maybe if it was done without my knowledge...” (KR04).

In another interview, a respondent revealed that:

“...at my level and generally the law enforcement bodies have no capabilities of monitoring and regulating gambling that is done online. Unless the government Tanzania Communication Regulatory Authority comes up with a way of regulating this online gambling then we can get sense out of it...” (KR02).

With the above findings, it can be summed as a weakness or failure by the GBT to effectively control teenagers from engaging in gambling activities. The mechanism for implementing the age restriction regulation was expected through creating awareness and consistent inspections in gaming areas. Also the fact that the GBT is not equipped to monitor and ensure that under age do not engage in gambling that is done online. These aspects were not being done as required of the board hence the continued influence of teenagers to get involved in gambling activities.

Figure 3. Effectiveness of DAS

Source: Field data, 2023

Effectiveness of DAS Office

As one of the roles of the DAS’s office, is to translate national legislation at district level. By

this, it shows how the office is mandated to make sure that gambling activities comply with age limit in gambling places. The study thus wanted to know whether the office of the DAS

is effective in creating awareness to the stakeholders about the laws, rules and regulations that hinder under age individuals from participating in gambling activities. The study therefore required the respondents to indicate the degree to which they agree to the statements and the results are shown in the figure 3 above.

The figure 3 above shows the findings on effectiveness of the office of DAS in controlling teenage involvement in gambling activities. On the part of awareness, the majority respondents indicated disagree (42%) followed by neutral (28%), strongly disagree (18%), agree (10%) and the minority respondents indicated strongly agree (2%).

In monitoring of compliance to age in gambling places, the majority responses indicated disagree (54%) followed by neutral (22%), agree (10%), strongly disagree (8%) and the minority respondents indicated strongly agree (2%).

The findings on effectiveness of the DAS office on controlling teenage involvement gambling revealed that there is a challenge. A majority 60% of the respondent indicated to disagree that the office creates awareness and again a majority of 62% indicated to disagree to the DAS monitoring of compliance to age restrictions in gambling premises. This was in line with the findings from the interviews that revealed that the office of the DAS has not been very instrumental in enforcing the age restriction regulations hence a vacuum that has influenced teenagers to get involved in the gambling activities. The revelation of online gambling done by teenagers as revealed from the office of the DAS was not any different from other interviewees since it was ascertained that the country has got a single agency TCRA that monitors use of communication gadgets. The study therefore discovered that the office of the DAS has not been effective in creating awareness and monitoring of gambling activities to ensure that teenagers are not involved in the activities.

Figure 4. Effectiveness of WEO

Source: Field data, 2023

Effectiveness of WEO

According to Raymond (2015), the Ward Executive Officer is the coordinating agent for

the local government administration acting between the district and the village councils. The WEO is therefore anticipated to carry on roles of the district council at the grass root level.

Thus the study wanted to investigate how the WEO plays role in controlling teenage involvement in gambling activities. The respondents were required to indicate in agreement or disagreement to the given statements. Findings are presented in the figure 4 above.

The figure 4.13 above shows the findings about the WEO in relation to controlling teenage involvement in gambling activities. About monitoring of the gambling places for under age or teenagers, the majority respondents indicated disagree (54%) followed by strongly disagree (18%), neutral (18%) and the minority respondents indicated agree (10%). There were no respondents who indicated strongly agree.

In apprehending the individuals who do not comply with age restrictions, the majority of respondents indicated disagree (78%) followed by strongly agree (10%), neutral (8%) while the minority respondents indicted strongly agree (2%) and agree (2%).

According to the interviews that were held, the WEO has not been effective in controlling teenage involvement in gambling. It was learned that at the ward level, still the WEO acts on intelligence given by the street executives and

good Samaritans. On this issue, the key informants revealed that it is a challenge to act where there is no information.

One interviewee from local authorities had to assert that

“...it is on rare occasion to see the WEO coming down to enforce the age thing in gambling places. In most cases we see police officers apprehending the youth playing ‘Kamali’ but this is normally after they are tipped off about drug abuse and suspected criminals. I think it is imperative that mechanisms are devised by the WEO to effectively monitor and bring to end teenage involvement in gambling...” (KR03).

With the results from the questionnaires where the vast majority disagreed to the WEO monitoring and apprehending teenagers gambling and their accomplices, the interviews as well augmented to the failures of the WEO to control teenage gambling not even mentioning the gambling by teenagers that is done in private using the smart phones and other electronic gadgets. The study thus determined that the WEO office failure to execute its mandate has influenced teenagers to engage in gambling activities.

Figure 5 Effectiveness of street government

Source: Field data, 2023

Effectiveness of street government

The major roles of the street government are to support the LGAs in promoting economic

development and service delivery to the local community. The roles go further in identifying the community needs and problems (Rugeiyamu

et al, 2019). The study thus anticipated that the street government monitor and takes steps by monitoring and reporting for apprehending culprits to law enforcement where there is a risk factor when the teenagers who are under age take part in gambling activities in the specific street areas. The study required the respondents to indicate the degree to which they agree with the statements given. Findings are presented in the figure 5 above.

The figure 5 above shows the findings on street government roles in controlling teenager involvement in gambling activities. On the role of monitoring gambling activities to control teenage involvement, the majority respondents indicated disagree (40%) followed by agree (22%), neutral (16%), strongly agree (14%) and the minority respondents indicated strongly disagree (8%).

The role of reporting of law breakers, the majority respondents indicated neutral (38%) followed by disagree (34%), strongly disagree (18%), and agree (6%) and the minority respondents indicated strongly agree (4%).

The outcomes show the majority of 40% disagree to the street government playing role by monitoring gambling activities and also a majority 52% disagree to the street government reporting non-compliance to age limits in gambling places. It is mere fact that the street government failure to execute this role has led to more teenagers engaging in gambling activities contrary to the law. The findings do not differ with the outcomes from the interviews that also revealed that the street government has not done enough to mitigate the community problem of under-age gambling practices.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the scrutinized factors have influence on teenagers' involvement in gambling activities in Tanzania. The legislative bodies have influence to either to control or to let acceleration of the problem of teenagers' engagement in gambling. The law in place once enforced by the mandated bodies, it de-escalates

the problem but if the law is not enforced, the problem escalates. With the TGA of 2006 in place, the failure of GBT, DAS' office, WEO and street governments to play role, it has influenced teenagers to engage in gambling activities in the areas where the study was conducted.

Recommendation

The study conclusions led to the following recommendations;

In collaboration with the Ministry of Education Science and Technology, the President's Office, Regional Administration and Local Government needs to come up with a policy awareness program through schools and learning institutions to educate the public on critical laws and policies like the age restriction law in gambling that are not complied to because of ignorance.

The government has got a law debt in ensuring that new technology in use is well monitored for compliance to the existing laws and is regulated. The TGA Of 2006 and its protocols do not cater for online gaming activities to a wider extent. This needs to be addressed at policy level and at the law enforcement level by equipping the mandated regulators with tools to effectively monitor the gambling activities done online as well as enforce the age restrictions. This calls for amendment in the cyber laws as well to explicitly expound on the areas of gambling

The government of Tanzania is advised to ensure that local government authorities at all levels get adequate training and capacity to ensure that they understand strategic issues that affect the communities, right from the grass root, not leaving out the aspect of advancing technology. This can be done more effectively through community policing and strategic intelligence.

The government also needs to develop mass awareness programs that aim at restoring sanity among parents to take on full responsibilities as parents. Parents should be educated and then made accountable for their children's behaviors

most especially the teens in this aspect when they are found engaging in activities that are restricted to them for their age.

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